

**CORRIGENDUM TO: ON THE PROBLEM OF UNIQUENESS FOR THE
MAXIMUM STIRLING NUMBER(S) OF THE SECOND KIND**

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Corrigendum

Concerning the statement of Lemma 1, a line of text was inadvertently omitted from the source file. This line indicated that the additional term $+O_*(n^{-1})$ should be part of the displayed equation, and that the equation should be labeled as equation number (5).